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Simulation of the tides around Norðoyggjar Faroe Islands.

- a report in the project
"New Fish Farming Locations in the Faroe Islands"

by

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1 Introduction

Fish farming on the Faroe Islands has increased considerably over the last two decades or so, and is now the second most important industry after the traditional fishing industry. Today nearly all areas traditionally considered as suitable for fish farming are in use. Waves and too strong tidal currents are the factors usually discarding areas for fish farming, but development of new farming equipment in recent years has to a large degree overcome the problem with too high waves. Too strong current limits the survival and growth of the fish and thus also the financial benefit. The main aim of this project is to find areas where the tidal currents are below given limits by means of current measurements, which are done by Landsverkfrøðingurin (LV), and of numerical tidal simulation, which is done by Náttúruvísindadeildini (NVD) at Fróðskaparsetur Føroya with subcontract to the Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC). Fiskirannsóknarstovan (FRS) contributes with data and general expertise. The project is coordinated by P/F Fiskaaling, who also is responsible for the marine biological and farming equipment tasks in this project.

The report presents simulation of the four main constituents of the tides in the area around Norðoyggjar with a barotropic tidal model (Section 2). The resolution of the main model domain is about 100 m, while the resolution in a subdomain is about 50 m (Section 3.2). The main model is forced by a model solution derived in a 0.5 *nautical miles* resolution simulation performed by a consortium of oil companies, FGEM, while the subdomain is forced by the solution from the 100 m resolution model (Section 3.1). The model results are run through an harmonic analyses similar to what is used on timeseries on measured data. A brief summary of this analysis is given in Section 2.2. The model results is validated towards tidal constituents for the elevation and current derived from measured data. The available observation station is presented in Section 3.3. The result of the simulation and the validation is presented for each model domain in Sections 4.1 – 4.2. The model results are presented as tidal charts, tidal current ellipse axis charts and, maximum current charts.

A request for accurate results from numerical simulation of the the tidal currents are accurate bottom depth matrixes. LV has mapped the bathymetry of many fjords and channels to a very high accuracy. Outside the inner waters, and also in some channels the spatial data coverage density is sparse in previous bathymetry maps, and the positioning of the data points is poor compared to modern positioning systems [Simonsen, 1998]. In order to generate the required depth matrixes a depth data logging program was organized on the research vessel *Magnus Heinasson* and later also on the Coast Guard and Rescue Vessel *Tjaldrið*. This data collection is shortly described in the present report (Section 3.2) as well the generation of the depth matrixes re-

quired for the simulation of the tides. The report is concluded in Section 7.

2 The numerical tidal model

2.1 Formulation

The applied tidal model is an improved version of the model by Simonsen [1992], which again is based on the models by Gjevik and Straume [1989] and Flather [1981, 1976]. The model is based on the depth integrated hydrodynamic equations, which in a Cartesian system with the axis x, y , and the corresponding volume transports (U, V) may be written:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \frac{U}{h} \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + \frac{V}{h} \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} - fV = -gh \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} + A_x + B_x \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + \frac{U}{h} \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{V}{h} \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} + fU = -gh \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} + A_y + B_y \quad (2)$$

where g is acceleration due to gravity, h is the mean depth, f is the Coriolis parameter and η is the vertical displacement of the sea surface from its undisturbed position. A_x, A_y are the components of the bottom friction, and B_x, B_y are the components of the lateral friction, which will be defined subsequently.

The continuity equation reads

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (3)$$

The bottom stress is parameterized by

$$A_x = -kU/h; A_y = -kV/h \quad (4)$$

where k is the bottom friction coefficient, which optionally is expressed in linear form,

$$k = c_D u_s \quad (5)$$

or on quadratic form

$$k = c_D [U^2 + V^2]^{1/2} / h \quad (6)$$

where u_s is a typical scale for the tidal current. In shallow water the bottom friction significantly influence the tidal propagation, while it is little influenced in water deeper than about 50 m [Prandle, 1997].

In shallow water applications [Holmes and Samarawickrama, 1995, Joensen and Hansen, 1991]e.g. the friction coefficient may be related to the water depth by the formulation

$$c_D = g/C^2 \quad (7)$$

where

$$C = \frac{1}{n}(h + \eta)^{1/6} \quad (8)$$

and n is known as the Manning number. With a typical n equal to 0.03 c_D would range from 0.004 to 0.002 for water depths of 10 m to 100 m. Typical values for c_D in large area models is within the range 0.0025–0.0030 [Gjevik, 1989, Glorioso and Flather, 1997, Flather, 1976, Kowalik and Proshutinsky, 1996], while Flather [1994] used 0.0015 for a model for relative shallow area in the Bay of Bengal. In the present simulations a constant $c_D = 0.0015$ is adopted.

The lateral friction is modeled by

$$B_x = \nu \nabla^2 U, B_y = \nu \nabla^2 V \quad (9)$$

where ν is the horizontal eddy viscosity. However, for the present applications the lateral friction is not included.

The equation of motion have been discretized on a space-staggered C-grid [Mesinger and Arakawa, 1976] using a forward-backward scheme usually credited to Sielecki [1968]. The dispersion and stability conditions for this scheme is discussed by Sielecki [1968], Martinsen et al. [1979] and by Simonsen [1992]. The advective terms are implemented by a forward centered scheme, which is known for its high diffusivity. However, the advective terms are not included in the 50 m resolution simulation. The model is implemented using a Mercator projection relative to the meridian running through the center of the model domain.

The model is spun up from an ocean in rest, e.g. no variation in the surface elevation and zero currents in all places. When the model has reached a state, where the tidal cycles starts to repeat themselves, the model is run for an additional given time interval, where time series for the surface elevation and the current components are generated in every grid point in the model. In order to derive the tidal parameters from the generated timeseries the model results are run through a similar analyses as used for measured data [Foreman, 1977].

2.2 Harmonic analysis of model results

The harmonic analysis of the model results is based on a least square fit [Foreman, 1977] of the amplitudes, A_j and phases, ϕ_j in the function

$$y_i = C_0 + \sum_{j=1}^M A_j \cos[2\pi\sigma_j t_i + \phi_j] \quad (10)$$

where C_0 is the residual, M is number of constituents, and σ_j is the frequency. This approach is used on the sea surface elevation and on the current components.

The tidal current may also be described as two rotating vectors expressed in complex notation as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{+}(t) &= \frac{1}{2}[(U \cos \phi_u + V \sin \phi_v) + i(V \cos \phi_v - U \sin \phi_u)]e^{i\sigma t} \\ R_{-}(t) &= \frac{1}{2}[(U \cos \phi_u - V \sin \phi_v) + i(V \cos \phi_v + U \sin \phi_u)]e^{-i\sigma t} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where the constituent subscript j is dropped, U, V and ϕ_u, ϕ_v is the amplitude and phase of the current components, respectively, and the subscript signs refer to the direction of the rotation. Combining these two rotating motions results into an ellipse, where the length of the major- and minor semi axis become

$$\begin{aligned} Vmax &= |\vec{R}_{+}| + |\vec{R}_{-}| \\ Vmin &= |\vec{R}_{+}| - |\vec{R}_{-}| \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The phases of the rotary motions are expressed by

$$\tan \phi_{\pm} = Im(R_{\pm})/Re(R_{\pm}) \quad (13)$$

and the phase of the net motion by

$$\phi = (\phi_{-} - \phi_{+})/2 \quad (14)$$

and the inclination of the maximum current relative to east is expressed by

$$\theta = (\phi_{-} + \phi_{+})/2 \quad (15)$$

3 Input and validation data

3.1 Open boundary data

The open boundary data, also known as the external solution for the 100 m resolution simulation is obtained from a tidal simulation with a 0.5 *nautical miles* resolution model done by NERSC for FGEM, which is a consortium of oil companies interested in exploitation of the area around the Faroe Islands [Simonsen, 1999]. The external solution for the regional area simulations is then obtained from the results of the 100 m resolution simulation. The included constituents are listed in Table 1.

3.2 Depth matrixes

At the start of the project data were available from LV and Jarðfrøðissavnið in addition to navigational maps. Other bathymetries like ETOP5, Gebco, and Westerberg [1990] were considered to be too coarse for present application. The datapoints in the Jarðfrøðissavnið-dataset are relatively sparse and the positioning was found to be questionable at several locations in coastal areas. The navigational maps were only available as hardcopy and it was noticed that they still includes depth loggings from early in this century with the accuracy available at that time.

The data set generated by LV provide a very detailed mapping of almost all fjords and many of the channels as well. In order to obtain data of sufficient accuracy and spatial density in the regions not covered by LV a depth measuring programme was organized in collaboration with FRS from January 1999, and from March 2000 also also with the Faroese Coast Guard and Rescue Service (Vaktar og Bjargingartænastan, V&B). Depth from the echo sounder on the vessels and the corresponding position is recorded every 5th second on *R/V Magnus Heinasson* and whenever the ship has moved 10 meter on the V&B vessel *Tjaldrið*. The positioning system on both vessels are based on DGPS and the accuracy is checked against a coastline provided by LV whenever the vessels docks in a harbour. The data are brought on shore after each cruise, where they are run through a filter process, which removes spikes and obvious errors data, and finally they are displayed graphically on a screen where they are manually inspected. For further details, please consult Simonsen [2000].

When the grid dimensions and model domain is decided, all available depth measurements within each grid cell is summed up and the mean and variance in each grid cell is calculated. The mean depth in each grid cell is used as the depth of the gridcell. The coast is defined by a coastline digitized by LV. The grid cell missing data are filled by a bilinear iterative interpolation routine. Along the coast the depth is set equal to the closest

Table 1: Symbol, name, and period of the constituents included in the simulations.

Symbol	Name	Period Hours
<i>Diurnal constituents</i>		
O ₁	Principal lunar diurnal	25.8192
K ₁	Luni-solar diurnal	23.9345
<i>Semi diurnal constituents</i>		
M ₂	Principal lunar	12.4206
S ₂	Principal solar	12.0000

gridcell within a radius of 4 gridcells. If no data exist within this radius then the depth toward the coast is interpolated from the closest data point within a radius of 1 km and 25 m or 3 m depth at the coast, depending on if the depth in the closest data point is deeper or shallower than 25 m. If no data exist within a radius of 1 km the depth at the coast is set equal to 25 m. The generated depth matrixes are presented in Figure 1 and further specifications are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Model depth matrixes and underlying bottom depth data sources.

Area	Resolution	Grid points	Undelying data
NA01, Figure 1, upper	100 m	399 x 399	LV, MH data to March 2000 and manually inserted data from navigational maps.
NA02, Figure 1, lower	50 m	499 x 469	LV, MH and V&B data to June 2000, and manually inserted data from navigational maps.

Figure 1: The model bathymetries with 100 m (upper) and 50 m (lower) resolution. The left hand plots shows gridpoints containing measured depth data, while the generated bathymetries are shown in the right hand plots. The contours are shown for every 10 m. Please consult Table 2 for details.

3.3 Validation data

The harmonic constants derived from measurements of the sea surface elevation is adopted from various sources listed Tables 3 and 4. Most of the data are found in the cited reports, while some data are measured and analysed as part of this project. An overview of the observation sites are presented in Figure 2

Figure 2: Water level measurement stations (circles) and current meter stations (ellipses). Details on each site is provided in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Tidal gauge stations where tidal harmonics are available for validation of the model. Empty space indicate that the actual information is not available.

St. No	Latitude			Longitude			Depth (m)		Dur. Days	Location	Source
	°	min	sec	°	min	sec	Inst	Bot.			
11	62	19	08	6	38	20	27		42	Haraldssund	Simonsen [1989]
12a	62	14	43	6	35	28				Klaksvík	Farvandsvæsenet [1998]
b	62	14	43	6	35	28				Klaksvík	LV, pers. comm.
13	62	12	47	6	42	22				Leivík	Farvandsvæsenet [1998]
W03	62	09	45	6	41	12				Gøta	LV, pers. comm.
W04	62	21	14	6	30	47				Eiðsvík	LV, pers. comm.
C24	62	21	23	6	51	42	86	86	139	Djúpini	LV, pers. comm.
C25	62	13	47	6	46	25	69	69	55	Fuglafirði	LV, pers. comm.
C26	62	20	39	6	28	15	63	86	32	Fugloyarfirði	LV, pers. comm.

Table 4: Current measurements stations where tidal harmonics are available for validation of the model.

St. No	Latitude			Longitude			Depth (m)		Dur. Days	Location	Source
	°	min	sec	°	min	sec	Inst	Bot.			
C02	62	10	30	6	42	07	6	40		Gøtuvík	Heinesen [2000]
C03	62	09	59	6	41	14	5	40		Gøtuvík	Heinesen [2000]
C04	62	11	08	6	41	02	15	40		Gøtuvík	Heinesen [2000]
C05	62	11	16	6	41	55	8	40		Gøtuvík	Heinesen [2000]
C19	62	17	49	6	56	05	7	45		Funningsfjørður	Heinesen [2000]
C20	62	17	42	6	56	38	3	45		Funningsfjørður	Heinesen [2000]
C21	62	18	05	6	55	13	6	40		Funningsfjørður	Heinesen [2000]
C22	62	16	21	6	56	39	1	30		Funningsfjørður	Heinesen [2000]
C23	62	13	19	6	46	59	30	8	139	Fuglafirði	Heinesen [2000]
C24	62	21	23	6	51	42	15	86	139	Djúpini	LV, pers. comm.
C25	62	13	47	6	46	25	39	69	39	Fuglafirði	LV, pers. comm.
C26	62	20	21	6	28	39	63	63	86	Fugloyarfirði	LV, pers. comm.

4 Model Results

The result from the simulations for the NA01 and NA02 areas are presented in Sections 4.1– 4.2, respectively. For each model domain are presented:

Tidal charts Maps presenting the elevation amplitude (cm) and Greenwich Phase Lag (degrees) of each constituent. Using the periods provided in Table 1 the delay of each constituent can be calculated to hours.

Current ellipse axis chart: Maps with the major and minor axis of the tidal current ellipses for each constituent. For definitions, please consult Section 2.2. For clarification they are only shown in every 10'th gridpoint. The speed is provided by a reference vector on each plot.

Maximum current maps: Contour plots of the length of the major semi axis in the current ellipses for each constituent, as well the sum of the major semi axis from the four included constituents, which shows the maximum current when all constituents are in phase.

It may be noted that constituents not included in the present simulations may be significant and actual maximum tidal currents may exceeds the estimates provided here. For details on each site please consult the sources listed in Table 4.

Model validation Comparison of the amplitude and Greenwich Phase Lag of the elevation and current ellipses parameters for each constituent.

The generated data, i.e. amplitude and Greenwich Phase Lag of the elevation and current ellipses parameters for each constituent are included on the attached CD-ROM.

4.1 Area NA01

4.1.1 Tidal Charts

Figure 3: Tidal charts derived from the 100m resolution model simulations for M₂, S₂, O₁ and, K₁. Solid line show the amplitude (cm s^{-1}) while dashed lines shows the Greenwich Phase Lag (degrees).

4.1.2 Tidal ellipses charts

Figure 4: Tidal current ellipse axis derived from the model simulations with 100 m resolution for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 . Note the different length scale of the ellipse axis.

4.1.3 Maximum current charts

Figure 5: Length of major semi ellipse axis derived from the model simulations with 100 m resolution for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 . Unit: cm s^{-1}

Figure 6: Sum of the major semi ellipse axis for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 as derived from the model simulations with 100 m resolution. Unit: cm s^{-1}

4.1.4 Validation of the 100 m resolution simulation

The amplitude and the Greenwich phase lag is compared in Table 5 and the tidal current ellipse parameters are compared in Table 6. Mean and standard deviation of the difference between the model and measured data derived parameters is provided for each constituent in the tables. Property-property plots of model and measured data parameters is provide in Figure 7.

In general the simulated elevation are in acceptual agreement with the measurements, although there are some deviations. The phase of the elevation for the K_1 -constituent differ in the range 23–39 degrees from the data based phase for all stations. This deviation is due to an offset of about 30 degrees in the data set used as the external solution. A relative large deviation in the phase may also be found for the S_2 -constituent at station W03 (Gøtuvík). This deviation may be related to an apparantly amphidromic point at Mjóvanes seen in Figure 3 for this constituent. For the amplitude a deviation of more than 10 cm may be noted for the M_2 at station 13, which indicate that the model does not simulate the extreme gradient in the M_2 -amplitude in Djúpini and Leirvíksfjörð perfectly. However, it may be noted, that the model does fairly well at the neighbouring sites, i.e. Gøtuvík, Fuglafirði and Klaksvík.

When comparing the model results with data from moored current meters the origin of the data must be included in the considerations. The model provides a depth averaged current, while the current meter provides the current at a particular depth. However, in strong currents the mooring may be pushed deeper by the current, which influence the depth and possible also the angle between the current direction and aniometer on the instrument. Although the tidal current at least theoretically may be considered as barotropic when the depth exceeds 50 m [Prandle, 1997] local barocline effects may influence the measured data in particular in areas with steep topography. Areas with changing bathymetry may not be properly represented in the model due to insufficient resolution, which implies that the model derived inclination and phase of the current motion differ considerably from the values derived from measured data.

Except for a couple of stations the simulated current is in acceptual agreement with the measurements. At station C24 (Djúpini) and at station C25 (Fuglafirði) the model current is much weaker than obtained by the measurements (compare the major axis for M_2). However, moving 2–3 grid cells (200–300 m) to the east and west on these two stations, respectively, then model current speeds are in good agreement with what is measured.

In particular close to the coast and in areas with complicated current pattern the model is expected to differ from the observations. In order to obtain correct direction of the current in particular close to the shore a very

detailed depth matrix is needed. With the given resolution the bathymetry may be too coarse at some sites, which is reflected by poor agreement between inclination and phase based on simulated and measured data.

Figure 7: Property–property plots of tidal elevation amplitude and Greenwich Phase Lag and the current ellipse parameters derived from measured and modelled generated data from the 100 m resolution simulation for M₂, S₂, O₁ and, K₁ constituents.

Table 5: Amplitude and Greenwich phase lag from measured data and from model generated data and the difference between these values for the M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 constituents. At the bottom of the table the mean and standard deviation of the difference for each parameter is provided for all four constituents

	O_1			K_1			M_2			S_2		
	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff
St. 11, Haraldssund												
Amp	9.7	7.6	2.1	9.1	6.0	3.1	47.8	48.2	-0.5	11.2	17.9	-6.7
Pha	20.0	28.1	-8.1	164.0	132.4	31.6	275.0	269.5	5.5	303.0	301.9	1.1
St. 12a, Klaksvík												
Amp	8.6	7.4	1.2	7.3	6.4	0.9	35.4	34.0	1.4	11.2	13.0	-1.8
Pha	30.0	32.9	-2.9	171.0	132.2	38.8	274.0	274.1	-0.1	309.0	306.9	2.1
St. 12b, Klaksvík												
Amp	8.8	7.4	1.4	6.7	6.4	0.3	35.8	34.0	1.8	11.5	13.0	-1.5
Pha	29.0	32.9	-3.9	163.0	132.2	30.8	272.0	274.1	-2.1	303.0	306.9	-3.9
St. 13, Leivík												
Amp	8.3	7.2	1.1	8.2	6.5	1.7	43.8	33.3	10.5	15.4	12.6	2.8
Pha	21.0	33.1	-12.1	169.0	132.7	36.3	275.0	270.5	4.5	307.0	302.7	4.3
St. W03, Gøta												
Amp	8.4	6.5	1.9	5.0	7.0	-2.0	16.0	12.9	3.1	5.1	4.1	1.0
Pha	45.0	35.8	9.2	133.0	130.2	2.8	277.0	279.0	-2.0	284.0	303.5	-19.5
St. W04, Eiðsvík												
Amp	8.7	7.2	1.5	6.0	6.6	-0.6	41.1	38.3	2.8	12.6	13.8	-1.2
Pha	30.0	34.6	-4.6	168.0	130.4	37.6	285.0	282.8	2.2	316.0	314.3	1.7
St. C24, Djúpini												
Amp	8.5	7.8	0.7	9.0	5.8	3.2	52.7	48.8	3.9	18.8	19.2	-0.4
Pha	16.0	26.8	-10.8	166.0	135.2	30.8	259.0	261.9	-2.9	289.0	296.4	-7.4
St. C25, Fuglafirði												
Amp	8.3	7.7	0.6	7.7	5.7	2.0	47.1	45.1	2.0	16.1	17.8	-1.7
Pha	13.0	27.8	-14.8	161.0	135.5	25.5	267.0	269.1	-2.1	299.0	302.9	-3.9
St. C26, Fugloyarfirði												
Amp	9.3	7.3	2.0	6.2	6.6	-0.4	40.8	38.9	1.9	12.8	14.0	-1.2
Pha	28.0	34.9	-6.9	154.0	131.0	23.0	283.0	284.9	-1.9	316.0	315.9	0.1
Amp		Mean	1.4			0.9			3.0			-1.2
Amp		St.dev.	0.5			1.7			3.1			2.6
Pha		Mean	-6.1			28.6			0.1			-2.8
Pha		St.dev.	7.0			11.0			3.2			7.3

Table 6: Length of major and minor semi axis, inclination and, net phase of current ellipses derived from measured data and from model generated data and the difference between these values for the for M₂, S₂, O₁ and, K₁ constituents . Negative minor semi axis indicate (clockwise) rotation. At the bottom of the table the mean and standard deviation of the difference for each parameter is provided for all four constituents

	O ₁			K ₁			M ₂			S ₂		
	Obs	Mod	Diff									
St. C02, Gøtuvík												
Maj	0.4	0.4	0.0	1.4	0.5	0.9	2.1	0.8	1.3	1.0	0.4	0.6
Min	0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.2	-0.3	0.0	-0.3	0.1	0.0	0.1
Inc	89.0	120.8	-31.8	97.0	115.4	-18.4	108.7	109.8	-1.1	104.7	111.3	-6.6
Pha	26.5	250.3	-223.8	248.8	314.7	-65.9	356.5	81.5	275.0	18.3	122.2	-103.9
St. C03, Gøtuvík												
Maj	1.7	1.2	0.5	3.2	1.4	1.8	6.8	1.5	5.3	3.2	0.6	2.6
Min	0.0	-0.1	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	0.0	-0.3	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1
Inc	119.3	133.7	-14.4	126.3	133.2	-6.9	124.7	140.2	-15.5	123.8	142.0	-18.2
Pha	7.8	322.1	-314.3	254.5	32.8	221.7	4.1	105.9	-101.8	42.7	165.0	-122.3
St. C04, Gøtuvík												
Maj	0.3	0.6	-0.3	1.1	0.9	0.2	1.1	1.4	-0.3	0.7	0.7	0.0
Min	0.1	-0.1	0.2	-0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.0	-0.3	0.3	0.0	-0.2	0.2
Inc	86.8	179.3	-92.5	82.7	175.5	-92.8	69.0	176.0	-107.0	79.3	175.4	-96.1
Pha	158.4	2.3	156.1	83.3	69.9	13.4	150.0	213.5	-63.5	195.5	245.8	-50.3
St. C05, Gøtuvík												
Maj	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.2	1.4	0.6	0.8	0.5	0.3	0.2
Min	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.4	0.0	-0.4	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Inc	13.3	5.0	8.3	102.7	7.5	95.2	179.2	2.7	176.5	174.0	5.5	168.5
Pha	116.1	196.7	-80.6	98.3	261.3	-163.0	140.6	44.3	96.3	158.7	80.5	78.2
St. C19, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.3	1.1	0.8	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.2
Min	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0
Inc	57.0	66.2	-9.2	146.4	76.4	70.0	42.1	47.0	-4.9	40.8	50.5	-9.7
Pha	190.3	317.8	-127.5	111.9	5.9	106.0	284.9	358.7	-73.8	295.6	29.0	266.6
St. C20, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.3
Min	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Inc	68.8	51.4	17.4	170.7	43.5	127.2	51.1	44.3	6.8	45.4	46.2	-0.8
Pha	162.9	44.8	118.1	136.7	298.3	-161.6	315.4	3.5	311.9	351.5	35.5	316.0
St. C21, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.7	0.2	0.5	3.3	2.3	1.0	1.9	1.2	0.7
Min	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.4	-0.3	0.7	0.1	-0.2	0.3
Inc	130.9	69.5	61.4	60.3	104.6	-44.3	57.9	64.6	-6.7	44.8	70.5	-25.7
Pha	160.9	52.9	108.0	199.5	254.9	-55.4	320.1	357.8	-37.7	336.7	26.7	310.0
St. C22, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	-0.2	0.1	0.2	-0.1
Min	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Inc	87.0	76.4	10.6	11.1	77.2	-66.1	65.7	78.4	-12.7	13.7	78.7	-65.0
Pha	169.2	123.8	45.4	284.6	229.0	55.6	317.6	353.7	-36.1	70.4	27.5	42.9

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	O ₁			K ₁			M ₂			S ₂		
	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff
St. C23, Fuglafirði												
Maj	2.0	0.5	1.5	0.7	0.8	-0.1	5.7	4.8	0.9	2.6	3.2	-0.6
Min	-0.9	0.0	-0.9	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-2.9	0.1	-3.0	-1.4	0.0	-1.4
Inc	156.4	132.9	23.5	153.3	135.5	17.8	140.0	140.0	0.0	147.9	142.9	5.0
Pha	167.0	232.1	-65.1	50.8	217.8	-167.0	268.7	283.2	-14.5	280.0	308.7	-28.7
St. C24, Djúpini												
Maj	4.3	8.0	-3.7	6.0	7.6	-1.6	30.8	12.8	18.0	13.6	5.0	8.6
Min	0.5	-1.9	2.4	0.0	1.1	-1.1	-25.0	-7.0	-18.0	-6.5	-1.9	-4.6
Inc	91.5	31.9	59.7	91.2	38.1	53.1	103.0	37.4	65.6	112.6	167.0	-54.4
Pha	151.1	294.6	-143.5	35.6	306.1	-270.5	162.9	206.8	-43.9	191.2	113.3	77.9
St. C25, Fuglafirði												
Maj	3.7	0.7	3.0	3.0	0.9	2.1	32.1	11.6	20.5	12.5	5.3	7.2
Min	2.1	0.1	2.0	0.5	0.2	0.3	5.6	1.6	4.0	2.5	1.2	1.3
Inc	96.1	123.1	-27.0	109.7	110.5	-0.8	82.5	100.8	-18.3	82.2	96.9	-14.7
Pha	313.8	33.8	280.0	240.4	342.6	-102.2	4.6	16.9	-12.3	21.7	40.3	-18.6
St. C26, Fugloyarfirði												
Maj	5.2	5.8	-0.6	5.2	1.1	4.1	51.4	56.5	-5.1	22.8	23.8	-1.0
Min	-1.0	0.3	-1.3	0.6	-0.2	0.8	-4.8	0.8	-5.6	-0.6	1.1	-1.7
Inc	144.9	136.0	8.9	127.3	118.5	8.8	138.9	129.1	9.8	138.3	126.5	11.8
Pha	5.2	52.6	-47.4	280.6	326.6	-46.0	62.0	44.2	17.8	84.9	63.2	21.7
Maj		Mean	0.1			0.7			3.5			1.6
Maj		St.dev.	1.5			1.4			7.7			3.1
Min		Mean	0.2			0.0			-1.9			-0.5
Min		St.dev.	1.0			0.5			5.6			1.5
Inc		Mean	1.2			11.9			7.7			-8.8
Inc		St.dev.	41.6			65.4			65.5			64.2
Pha		Mean	-24.5			-52.9			26.5			65.8
Pha		St.dev.	171.1			136.1			134.5			153.5

4.2 Area NA02

4.2.1 Tidal Charts

Figure 8: Tidal charts derived from the model simulations with 50 m resolution for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 . Solid line show the amplitude (cm s^{-1}) while dashed lines shows the Greenwich Phase Lag (degrees).

4.2.2 Tidal ellipses charts

Figure 9: Tidal current ellipse axis derived from the model simulations with 50 m resolution for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 . Note the different length scale of the ellipse axis.

4.2.3 Maximum current charts

Figure 10: Length of major semi ellipse axis derived from the model simulations with 50 m resolution for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 . Unit: cm s^{-1}

Figure 11: Sum of the major semi ellipse axis for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 as derived from the model simulations with 50 m resolution. Unit: cm s^{-1}

4.2.4 Validation of the 50 m resolution simulation

The amplitude and Greenphase Lag is compared in Table 6 and the tidal current ellipse parameters are compared in Table 7. Mean and standard deviation of the difference between the model and measured data derived parameters is provided for each constituents in the tables. Property-property plots of model and measured data parameters is provide in Figure 12.

For the elevation the simulation shows only small changes in the diurnal tide. Since the boundary condition is adopted from the results of 100 m resolution the bias in the phase in the K_1 tide is also in the present simulation. For the semidiurnal tide a generally better improvement is obtained for St. 13 (Leirvík) compared with the 100 m resolution. At St. C25 (Fuglafirði) the amplitude is reduced, and the model has now a slightly larger under estimation of the M_2 at this station, while the amplitude of S_2 is in complete agreement. At St. W03 (Gøtuvík) the semidiurnal amplitudes are increased, and the model is now slightly over estimating the semi diurnal amplitudes with 0.4-1.2 cm. This implies that the gradient through southern Kalsoyar- and Leirvíksfjørð is less pronounced in the higher resolution simulation. For the S_2 relative large deviation at St. W03 is also the case in the 50 m resolution simulation. As for the 100 m resolution this is most likely related to an amphidromic point which is somewhere at Mjóvanes (Figure 3) or further south close to point Nev just south of Lambavík (Figure 8). In general the mean deviation is in the range from -0.3 cm for the (S_2), to 3.1 cm (M_2) and the standard deviation is in the range 0.4–3.4 cm for the four included constituents.

Except for St. 25 the current stations are all in relative slack water in Gøtuvík and Funningsfjørð and close to the shore. The results at these stations are quite similar for the two simulations. At St. 25 it may be noted that the deviation in speed is larger in the 100 m resolution simulation, but if compared with the results about 200 m further east the speed is compareable. For the net phase it may be noted that the deviation is close to 180° out of phase at several stations. Since the elevation is in fairly good agreement it is likely that the main currents also are fairly close to the reality, so this may indicate that some of the actual stations are in areas of counter currents, which are not resolved by the model or the model is otherwise not generating the counter currents due to its shortcomings in resolution and numerics. In general the simulated speed is found to be fairly representative for the area, although the model seems to underestimate the speed at stations which are close to the shore.

Whe comparing the plots of the sum of major semi ellipse axis for the two simulations (Figures 6 and 11) a striking difference is seen in the area where the sum exceeds 2.50 m s^{-1} in Leirvíks- and Kalsoyarfjørð as well in the area around Mjóvanes. This is related to the change in the gradient

Table 6: Amplitude and Greenwich phase lag from measured data and from model generated data and the difference between these values for the M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 constituents. At the bottom of the table the mean and standard deviation of the difference for each parameter is provided for all four constituents

	O_1			K_1			M_2			S_2		
	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff
St. 12a, Klaksvík												
Amp	8.6	7.3	1.3	7.3	6.7	0.6	35.4	33.7	1.7	11.2	12.6	-1.4
Pha	30.0	32.5	-2.5	171.0	133.4	37.6	274.0	266.0	8.0	309.0	298.2	10.8
/bf St. 12b, Klaksvík												
Amp	8.8	7.3	1.5	6.7	6.7	0.0	35.8	33.7	2.1	11.5	12.6	-1.1
Pha	29.0	32.5	-3.5	163.0	133.4	29.6	272.0	266.0	6.0	303.0	298.2	4.8
St. 13, Leivík												
Amp	8.3	7.6	0.7	8.2	6.1	2.1	43.8	36.5	7.3	15.4	13.8	1.6
Pha	21.0	31.4	-10.4	169.0	132.7	36.3	275.0	272.1	2.9	307.0	306.0	1.0
St. W03, Gøtuvík												
Amp	8.4	7.1	1.3	5.0	6.9	-1.9	16.0	17.2	-1.2	5.1	5.5	-0.4
Pha	45.0	36.9	8.1	133.0	129.1	3.9	277.0	283.1	-6.1	284.0	310.3	-26.3
St. C25, Fuglafirði												
Amp	8.3	7.7	0.6	7.7	5.9	1.8	47.1	41.5	5.6	16.1	16.1	0.0
Pha	13.0	29.5	-16.5	161.0	134.5	26.5	267.0	268.8	-1.8	299.0	303.6	-4.6
Amp	Mean		1.1			0.5			3.1			-0.3
Amp	St.dev.		0.4			1.6			3.4			1.2
Pha	Mean		-5.0			26.8			1.8			-2.9
Pha	St.dev.		9.2			13.6			5.7			14.2

in the elvation mentioned above. The difference between the simulations may partly be due to the resolution and consequently change in numerical dissipation, and because the advection term is not included in the 50 m resolution simulation, which is reflected by smoother contoure lines in the plots from this simulation. Which of these simulations are generally most reliable is not possible to deduce since no measurements are within the areas with the largest deviations, although some conclusions may be reached locally where measurements are available. In order to obtain a more reliable result requires additional current measurements and simulation experiments, where the effect of changing bottom friction and dissipation is explored, but this is beyond the time frame of the present project.

Table 7: Length of major and minor semi axis, inclination and, net phase of current ellipses derived from measured data and from model generated data and the difference between these values for the for M₂, S₂, O₁ and, K₁ constituents . Negative minor semi axis indicate (clockwise) rotation. At the bottom of the table the mean and standard deviation of the difference for each parameter is provided for all four constituents

	O ₁			K ₁			M ₂			S ₂		
	Obs	Mod	Diff									
St. C02, Gøtuvík												
Maj	0.4	0.0	0.4	1.4	0.0	1.4	2.1	0.6	1.5	1.0	0.2	0.8
Min	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.3	0.1	-0.4	0.1	0.0	0.1
Inc	89.0	159.3	-70.3	97.0	1.9	95.1	108.7	122.2	-13.5	104.7	120.7	-16.0
Pha	26.5	285.1	-258.6	248.8	211.5	37.3	356.5	166.0	190.5	18.3	200.2	-181.9
St. C03, Gøtuvík												
Maj	1.7	0.1	1.6	3.2	0.1	3.1	6.8	1.8	5.0	3.2	0.7	2.5
Min	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.3	0.1	-0.4	-0.2	0.0	-0.2
Inc	119.3	147.1	-27.8	126.3	138.4	-12.1	124.7	129.1	-4.4	123.8	129.3	-5.5
Pha	7.8	261.1	-253.3	254.5	120.4	134.1	4.1	155.6	-151.5	42.7	190.3	-147.6
St. C04, Gøtuvík												
Maj	0.3	0.0	0.3	1.1	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.2	0.5
Min	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
Inc	86.8	169.1	-82.3	82.7	172.1	-89.4	69.0	8.0	61.0	79.3	8.4	70.9
Pha	158.4	320.8	-162.4	83.3	32.3	51.0	150.0	156.7	-6.7	195.5	198.7	-3.2
St. C05, Gøtuvík												
Maj	0.4	0.0	0.4	0.5	0.0	0.5	1.4	0.2	1.2	0.5	0.1	0.4
Min	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.4	0.0	-0.4	-0.2	0.1	-0.3	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Inc	13.3	139.8	-126.5	102.7	160.6	-57.9	179.2	9.9	169.3	174.0	15.3	158.7
Pha	116.1	336.1	-220.0	98.3	36.7	61.6	140.6	129.3	11.3	158.7	171.9	-13.2
St. C19, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.3	1.1	0.4	0.7	0.6	0.2	0.4
Min	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Inc	57.0	48.0	9.0	146.4	60.0	86.4	42.1	94.5	-52.4	40.8	98.1	-57.3
Pha	190.3	150.7	39.6	111.9	213.5	-101.6	284.9	147.5	137.4	295.6	184.3	111.3
St. C20, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.6	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.4
Min	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.2	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
Inc	68.8	29.9	38.9	170.7	33.2	137.5	51.1	17.5	33.6	45.4	169.6	-124.2
Pha	162.9	144.1	18.8	136.7	245.7	-109.0	315.4	43.2	272.2	351.5	216.7	134.8
St. C21, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.7	0.2	0.5	3.3	2.1	1.2	1.9	0.9	1.0
Min	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.4	0.1	0.0	0.1
Inc	130.9	48.5	82.4	60.3	78.6	-18.3	57.9	80.1	-22.2	44.8	81.1	-36.3
Pha	160.9	159.5	1.4	199.5	161.0	38.5	320.1	145.1	175.0	336.7	177.4	159.3
St. C22, Funningsfjørður												
Maj	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.4	-0.2	0.1	0.2	-0.1
Min	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Inc	87.0	74.6	12.4	11.1	77.0	-65.9	65.7	78.4	-12.7	13.7	78.4	-64.7
Pha	169.2	37.2	131.9	284.6	158.5	126.1	317.6	352.5	-34.9	70.4	33.4	37.0

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	O ₁			K ₁			M ₂			S ₂		
	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff	Obs	Mod	Diff
St. C23, Fuglafirði, Presttangi												
Maj	2.0	0.2	1.8	0.7	0.3	0.4	5.7	3.2	2.5	2.6	1.3	1.3
Min	-0.9	0.0	-0.9	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-2.9	0.1	-3.0	-1.4	0.0	-1.4
Inc	156.4	148.3	8.1	153.3	147.8	5.5	140.0	151.0	-11.0	147.9	151.1	-3.2
Pha	167.0	189.1	-22.1	50.8	140.5	-89.7	268.7	142.5	126.2	280.0	182.5	97.5
St. C25, Fuglafirði, Pollinum												
Maj	3.7	0.6	3.1	3.0	0.8	2.2	32.1	8.1	24.0	12.5	3.3	9.2
Min	2.1	0.1	2.0	0.5	0.1	0.4	5.6	0.9	4.7	2.5	0.4	2.1
Inc	96.1	106.7	-10.6	109.7	106.8	2.9	82.5	106.9	-24.4	82.2	107.0	-24.8
Pha	313.8	204.1	109.7	240.4	153.1	87.3	4.6	147.6	-143.0	21.7	187.2	-165.5
Maj		Mean	0.8			1.0			3.7			1.7
Maj		St.dev.	1.0			1.0			7.3			2.7
Min		Mean	0.1			0.0			0.1			0.0
Min		St.dev.	0.7			0.2			1.9			0.9
Inc		Mean	-16.7			8.4			12.3			-10.2
Inc		St.dev.	61.9			75.2			63.5			77.7
Pha		Mean	-61.5			23.6			57.6			2.9
Pha		St.dev.	149.0			91.6			144.3			128.7

Figure 12: Property–property plots of tidal elevation amplitude and Greenwich Phase Lag and the current ellipse parameters derived from measured and modelled generated data from the 50 m resolution simulation for M_2 , S_2 , O_1 and, K_1 constituents.

5 Data base

A file is produced containing amplitude and Greenwich phase lag of the tidal elevation and current components for each of the eight constituents, and a file containing length of major semi axis, length of minor semi axis, inclination relative to east, and net Greenwich phase lag, i.e. the tidal current ellipses parameter for each of the eight constituents. The name of the files are listed in Table 7.

The format of the files are:

```
VARIABLES="h_pha_M2"  
ZONE I=555,J=455,F=BLOCK  
0.16328E+03 0.16328E+03 0.16333E+03 0.16338E+03 0.16343E+03 0.16348E+03  
0.16353E+03 0.16358E+03 0.16362E+03 0.16367E+03 0.16372E+03 0.16377E+03  
0.16382E+03 0.16387E+03 0.16393E+03 0.16398E+03 0.16403E+03 0.16408E+03  
0.16413E+03 0.16418E+03 0.16424E+03 0.16429E+03 0.16434E+03 0.16439E+03  
0.16444E+03 0.16449E+03 0.16455E+03 0.16460E+03 0.16465E+03 0.16470E+03  
0.16475E+03 0.16480E+03 0.16486E+03 0.16492E+03 0.16499E+03 0.16505E+03  
0.16512E+03 0.16518E+03 0.16525E+03 0.16532E+03 0.16538E+03 0.16545E+03  
. . .
```

where the header is as required by the Tecplot graphical software from Amtec Engineering, Inc. The header provide variable name and size of file. Land points are given the value $1E+36$. The data are written using following Fortran code:

```
WRITE(10,'(6e12.4)')((array(j,k),j=1,jj),k=1,kk)
```

where *array* has the dimension of (ii,jj) (See Table 2 for actual values). If more than one variable is included, then they are listed in the header and the data for each variable are included sequentially in the block format shown above. The files in the database and a short description of their content is listed in Table 7.

Table 7: File names and content in the data base. *xx* is constituent symbol. Data from the two model domains are found in sub-directories Na01 and Na02, respectively.

File name	Content
<i>h_amp_xx.res</i>	Amplitude (cm) for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>h_pha_xx.res</i>	Greenwich phase lag ($^{\circ}$) for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>h_000_00.res</i>	The residual tidal elevation
<i>u_amp_xx.res</i>	Amplitude (cm s^{-1}) of the <i>u</i> velocity component for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>u_pha_xx.res</i>	Greenwich phase lag ($^{\circ}$) of the <i>u</i> velocity component for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>u_000_00.res</i>	The <i>u</i> component of the residual current
<i>v_amp_xx.res</i>	Amplitude (cm s^{-1}) of the <i>v</i> velocity component for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>v_pha_xx.res</i>	Greenwich phase lag ($^{\circ}$) of the <i>v</i> velocity component for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>v_000_00.res</i>	The <i>v</i> component of the residual current
<i>E_maj_xx.res</i>	Length (mm s^{-1}) of major semi axis for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>E_min_xx.res</i>	Length (mm s^{-1}) of minor semi axis for the <i>xx</i> -tide
<i>E_dir_xx.res</i>	Inclination ($^{\circ}$) of the major axis relative to east
<i>E_pha_xx.res</i>	Phase of the net current motion ($^{\circ}$)
<i>ellip_xx.res</i>	The vector components (<i>v1,v2</i>) of the major and minor axis in a east-north Cartesian system.
<i>depth_iixjj.dat</i>	Depth matrix, where <i>iixjj</i> refer to the model grid dimension.
<i>diracc02.dat</i>	Fortran direct access file, which contains all files above except <i>ellip_xx.res</i> and <i>depth_iixjj.dat</i> .

6 Interactive tidal presentation

This effort is to provide an interactive and graphical front-end to present results from tidal models. The presentation includes color versions of all figures in the present report in colors in addition to some additional figures. For the plots of maximum currents (Figures 6 and 11) a primitive zooming facility is incorporated. The presentation is based on the html language and should be readable with a WWW browser.

7 Conclusion

An about 100 m resolution tidal model is run for the area around Norðoyggjar for the four of the most important constituents. The results from this simulation is then used along the open boundaries in a regional model domain with 50 m resolution which cover the northern Kalsoyarfjörð, Leirvíksfjörð, Djúpini and adjacent fjords and bays.

In the initial phase of the project it was realized that existing bottom maps could not reach the requirement for accurate tidal simulation with the resolution used in the present work except for the fjords and sounds covered by the bottom depth measuring program by LV in recent years. An cooperative effort was initiated by FRS and NVD, and later also V&B to log depth data and corresponding along the track of the R/V Magnus Heinasson and the V&B vessel Tjaldrið. Using about 18 months of data logged by R/V Magnus Heinasson and about 3 months of data logged by V&B vessel Tjaldrið in combination with data from LV fairly accurate depth matrixes are generated for application in the present report (Section 3.2). There are still areas, where bottom depth measurements are scarce and the initiated bottom depth measurement effort is planned to continue also after the complementation of the present project.

Tidal harmonics based on measurements by tidal gauges and current meters are collected from various available sources, including very recent measurements performed by LV and analysed in a cooperative effort by LV, FRS and NVD (Section 3.3), and presented in Sections 4.1 and 4.2.

The model results are validated towards the measurement data (Section 4.1.4, Tables 5 and 6, and Section 4.2.4, Tables 6 and 7). In general the elevation and the current is found to be in good agreement with the measurements, while larger deviations is found for the inclination and net phase of the tidal current ellipses. However, this is partly expected due to shortcomings of the model arising from the nature of the digitized representation of the bathymetry in the model.

The results are presented as:

- tidal charts for each constituent,

- tidal current ellipse axis maps for each constituent,
- extreme tidal current maps,

The graphic presentation of the model results and the data base is incorporated into a interactive presentation system developed in html, which is platform independent. The presentation system includes color versions of all figures in this report and some additional figures, the validation of the model, this report in pdf-format and a database containing the amplitude and phase of the elevation and the tidal current ellipses parameters in the entire model domain for the four constituents included in the present work.

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